

PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPING MODERN TOURISM IN TASHKENT TODAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17139118>

***Abstract.** This article states that tourism has become a priority field in the world today, and great attention is being paid to historical objects and shrines as world material heritage. At the same time, during the years of independence, the study of the life and activity of scholars in Uzbekistan, the holding of their jubilees, and the restoration of the architectural monuments in which their memory rests have been shown on the example of Tashkent city. Currently, the reforms carried out in Uzbekistan regarding the development of cultural, ecological and gastronomic tourism are widely covered.*

***Keywords:** tourism, object, shrine, monument, alloma, anniversary, reform, ecological, gastronomy.*

Introduction

Pilgrimage tourism, which is part of global tourism, is widely practiced internationally. Pilgrimage tourism sites encompass objects of historical, spiritual, and educational significance within a country that attract people's attention, such as historical monuments and places associated with great personalities. Pilgrimage tourism has been developing in our republic since ancient times. During the colonial and Soviet rule in the territory of Uzbekistan, visits to pilgrimage sites were suppressed. The tombs of scholars were left to fall into ruin. These sites were repurposed as warehouses and storage facilities.

It is known that there are three recognized categories of tourism in the world: international tourism, national tourism, and domestic tourism. In terms of thematic focus, there are several types of tourism, including tourism aimed at studying historical monuments and history, pilgrimage tourism, ethnographic tourism, ecological tourism, educational tourism, sports tourism, and other recreational forms of tourism. On September 25, 1996, Resolution No. 335 «On the establishment of the Department of International Cooperation in the field of culture, science and tourism in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan» was issued. Subsequently, in 1997, a plan for the sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan was developed. This plan, in turn, also encompassed pilgrimage tourism. [1].

Based on the aforementioned measures, during the years of independence, alongside the organization of internationally significant events under the auspices of UNESCO dedicated to the activities of saints and scholars buried in sacred sites, conducting scientific research was established as a primary objective. As a result, the 2500th anniversary of Termez, the 2700th anniversary of Shakhrisabz, the 2700th anniversary of Karshi, and the 2200th anniversary of Tashkent were commemorated.

Sacred pilgrimage sites, which are an integral part of the national spirituality and history of the Uzbek people, are inextricably linked with the names of famous individuals who have left an indelible mark on the history and culture of Uzbekistan. The promotion of their incomparable

heritage among the population holds great spiritual and educational significance today. There are more than seven thousand monuments in the republic, including 2,500 architectural monuments, over 2,700 archaeological sites, and more than a thousand monumental art pieces under state protection. In light of this, the decree No. 938 issued by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, on August 7, 2008, demonstrated the importance of efforts undertaken to preserve and improve sacred sites and establish a charitable foundation [2:12-32].

As an equal member of UNESCO, the Republic of Uzbekistan has had 13 renowned monuments registered with the International World Cultural Heritage Committee. These include the monuments located in the Ichan-Kala Reserve in Khiva (1990) and in the historical center of Bukhara (1993), the architectural monuments of the Timur and Timurid era in Shakhrisabz (2001), and the historical monuments in the center of Samarkand (2002) [3:4-5].

Under the leadership of I.A. Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, extensive restoration, construction, and renovation work was carried out at the Hazrati Imam religious and architectural complex in 2006-2007, including the construction of a new congregational mosque.

At the same time, the mausoleum of Sheikh Zayniddin Bobo from the 13th-19th centuries, the mausoleums of Yunus Khan and Sheikh Khovandi Tohur from the 15th century, the Kukaldosh Madrasa from the 16th century, the Khoja Alambardor Mausoleum from the 19th century, and the Sheikh Abulqosim Madrasa have undergone a complete transformation from their appearance 15-20 years ago. As a result, the capital city has restored its historical monuments and created an urban ensemble, executed in the latest traditions of national architecture [4:80].

Construction of the current building of the «Khoja Alambardor» congregational mosque began in 1993 and was completed in 2005. The mosque was officially registered with certificate No. 79 issued by the Tashkent City Justice Department on August 7, 1998, and certificate No. 09-006856 issued by the Tashkent City Administration on July 21, 1998.

Construction of the current mosque building began in 1993 and was completed in 2005. Renovation work on the mosque's old prayer hall commenced in 2009, with experienced craftsmen and carpenters from all regions of our country contributing their labor to the mosque. On Friday, July 22, 2011, Friday prayers were held for the first time in this mosque's renovated old prayer hall.

In 2007, the Islamic Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (ISESCO) declared Tashkent the capital of Islamic culture. This was yet another international recognition of the results of the goal-oriented work being carried out in our country to restore and preserve Islamic culture and spiritual values.

Tashkent fully lives up to this honorable title.

All of Tashkent's achievements are a worthy testament to Uzbekistan's comprehensive development.

In 2009, in connection with Tashkent's 2200th anniversary, the restoration of the Suzukota mausoleum was included in the list of jubilee projects by Uzbekistan's first president Islam Karimov. The exterior wall of the mausoleum was covered with polished bricks, and the interior walls were refinished and renovated. It should be noted that during the construction of the shrine complex, the mausoleum built in recent years, specifically in 1997-1998, was demolished to reveal its lower level. This area was studied with the participation of archaeologists, left exposed, and a staircase leading down was constructed. The mausoleum was restored to its original appearance.

The territory of the present-day Suzuk ota mahalla was formerly composed of several small mahallas. These included the mahallas of Chukur koprik, Mirlar, Andijan, and Chakar. Each of these neighborhoods had small guzar mosques. These mosques were preserved until recent years. The Mirlar Mosque was built in 1812, the Andijan Mosque in 1817, and the Chakar Mosque in 1820. [5:17].

On March 24, 2004, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution regarding the celebration of the 600th anniversary of Khoja Ahror's birth [6].

In 2017, following the directive of our President, extensive repair and restoration work was carried out at the complex to commemorate the 800th anniversary of the birth of Suzuk-ota, the grandson of Ahmad Yassavi. At present, the Suzuk-ota historical architectural complex has been transformed into a pilgrimage site.

In recent years, the tourism sector has become a stable source of revenue that influences the economic, social, and political development of countries. Its expansion not only helps preserve domestic national relations but also serves to showcase the cultural history of the state and its people in international relations. According to the United Nations, the annual increase in the number of tourists leads to a significant rise in various countries' contributions to their gross domestic product (GDP), highlighting the important role of tourism in today's economy [7:31-39].

According to calculations by countries worldwide, in 2017 the number of Muslim pilgrims globally reached 131 million, with revenue from this sector amounting to 142 million dollars. It is expected that by 2020, the number of pilgrims will reach 160 million, and by 2026, the profit generated from the pilgrimage tourism industry will reach 300 billion dollars [8].

It is worth noting that, by leveraging such opportunities in tourism, we can develop the international tourism market in our republic, shape it according to world standards, and thereby further enhance our economy. In the international tourism market, amidst intense competition, achieving the intended goals requires, first and foremost, a clear direction, continuous exploration, and organization of activities at the level of global standards.

It should be noted that in our country, there are more than 4,000 historical and architectural monuments [9] that have historical, cultural, architectural, and archaeological significance and can attract tourists. Of these, 140 objects are officially recognized as tourist attractions [10:42-45].

Experts emphasize that Uzbekistan has significant potential for developing all areas of tourism. Pilgrimage tourism routes serve as an additional source of income for the local population. For instance, by the end of 2019, Uzbekistan received \$1.3 billion from services provided across all sectors of tourism. This figure is 30% higher compared to 2018 [11:128-122]. Furthermore, tourism plays a crucial role in ensuring employment for the population. It is projected that by 2023, the tourism industry will directly employ 145,000 people [12:35-44].

Tourism has become a priority sector today. Our country has high potential in this area. This research serves, to a certain extent, in implementing the tasks specified in the following normative legal documents: Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5611 of January 5, 2019 «On Additional Measures for the Accelerated Development of Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan», No. UP-6165 of February 9, 2021 «On Measures for the Development of Domestic and Pilgrimage Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan,» No. PP-5232 of August 25, 2021 «On Additional Measures to Support the Spheres of Public Catering and Tourism», No. PP-338 of July 29, 2022 «On Measures for the Accelerated Development of Cooperation with Turkic States in the Field of Tourism», No. PP-135 of April 26, 2023 «On Additional Measures for the Accelerated Development of the Tourist Potential of the Republic and Further Increase in the

Number of Domestic and Foreign Tourists», No. PP-114 of July 27, 2023 «On Measures for the Effective Organization of State Management in the Field of Culture and Tourism within the Framework of Administrative Reforms», as well as Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 289 of July 29, 2022 «On Measures to Further Improve the Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects», and No. 100 of February 24, 2023 «On Additional Measures for the Development of Domestic and Pilgrimage Tourism».

On July 29, 2022, Presidential Decree No. UP-338 «On Measures for the Accelerated Development of Cooperation with Turkic States in the Field of Tourism» was adopted.

The decree approved the «Tabarruk ziyorat» (Sacred Pilgrimage) tourism concept within the framework of the Turkic world[13].

According to Appendix No. 5 of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-135 dated April 26, 2023, regarding the Action Plan for Tourism Development in Tashkent City in 2023, in the direction of attracting foreign tourists:

Attracting 4.2 million foreign tourists to Tashkent city,
including more than 2.5 million based on 1868 agreements signed within the framework of the XXVII Tashkent International Tourism Fair, specifically:

700 thousand people in the fields of medical, educational, and pilgrimage tourism;
500 thousand people through the organization of international forums, exhibitions, and conferences;

attracting 500 thousand tourists through mass entertainment events,
Establishing the activities of 20 tour operators and travel agents serving foreign tourists in Tashkent city.

Based on agreements with sister cities, including St. Petersburg, Baku, Tel Aviv, Seoul, Nagoya, and others, it is planned to showcase videos promoting the tourism potential of Tashkent on outdoor advertising media in foreign countries.

Creation of a special platform for 360-degree virtual online tours of Tashkent city's unique nature, recreational and entertainment venues, pilgrimage sites, ethnographic and gastronomic attractions;

Approval of measures to develop and promote a modern and recognizable tourist brand for the city of Tashkent;

Organization of info-tours to tourist sites in Tashkent with the participation of foreign media representatives, bloggers, and celebrities;

Development of an application for virtual online tours of the Tashkent metro;
In this regard, the task has been set to develop an electronic map providing information on virtual online tours of the Tashkent metro, as well as tourist, social, and other facilities.

Within the framework of this resolution, according to the «Travel around Uzbekistan» program: - Implement measures to organize trips for 1,920,000 residents of Tashkent city across the regions of the republic, and attract 4.3 million local tourists to Tashkent city;

Take measures to involve 300,000 people in the implementation of memorandums signed with 8 regions;

Organize mass entertainment events and facilitate visits of over 700,000 people through medical tourism;

Take measures to attract 1.5 million people by developing historical educational and cultural-entertainment tourism for youth, pupils, and students of educational institutions;

Take measures to attract 1 million people by widely promoting business, extreme, ecological, and gastronomic types of tourism for labor and neighborhood communities;

Attract 300,000 people by organizing pilgrimage, educational, social, cultural-entertainment, and ecological tourism events for women, as well as organizing trips for 1,920,000 residents of Tashkent city across the regions of the republic.

Development of tourism business activities in the city of Tashkent.

Establishment of a total of 84 accommodation facilities, including 38 hotels, 20 hostels, 20 family guesthouses, and 6 other infrastructure facilities.

Conducting an inventory of all hotels and facilities created for tourists in Tashkent city, as well as compiling a list of high-potential hotels and assigning them star ratings.

Compiling a list of capable restaurants, cafes, and bars that can provide high-quality service to tourists, offering European, Asian, and Uzbek national dishes, and introducing a «tourist-friendly environment certificate» for them.

As part of the summer season projects, it is planned to create a swimming area in a section of the lake within the «New Uzbekistan Park» territory.

Installing information boards inside the «Hazrati Imam» complex that explain pilgrimage etiquette and procedures, in order to provide additional services for tourists.

Around the site, along routes leading from the city center, metro stations, and other major shopping and entertainment centers to pilgrimage sites, the installation of directional signs and information markers is planned [14].

To promote tourism development, a Presidential Decree «On measures for effective organization of state management in the sphere of culture and tourism within the framework of administrative reforms» (No. UP-114, dated July 27, 2023) was also adopted.

According to the Decree, the following have been established:

The Ministry of Culture, based on the former Ministry of Culture and Tourism; and the Tourism Development Committee under the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change [15].

The promising reforms being implemented in our country to improve tourism not only create favorable conditions for foreign tourists but also play a crucial role in establishing our country's worthy position in the global community through the tourism market. According to World Tourism Organization forecasts, by 2030, the number of travelers will exceed 1.5 billion people, with expected revenue reaching 5.0 trillion dollars. This indicator, in turn, will have an impact on the increase in the number of tourists in our country.

Uzbekistan has been recognized as the best country in Central Asia in terms of tourist safety. Kazakhstan, on the other hand, ranked highest in the region for the quality of medical services provided to tourists. This conclusion was drawn by specialists from the International SOS organization, which specializes in providing safety and medical services to tourists.

The Statistics Agency has reported the number of foreign citizens who visited Uzbekistan for commercial purposes in the last 11 months. According to the report, a total of 61,100 foreign citizens visited Uzbekistan for commercial purposes in the last 11 months of this year.

Additionally, the countries whose citizens most frequently visited Uzbekistan for commercial purposes from January to November were as follows:

Turkmenistan - 39,342 people, Tajikistan - 13,474 people, Turkey - 947 people, China - 916 people, South Korea - 563 people, and 5,824 citizens from other countries arrived in Uzbekistan for commercial purposes.

Tourism is a comprehensive sector with both economic and socio-cultural significance, ranking third in the world in terms of profitability. Another important aspect is that it offers the possibility to create many jobs with low investment.

According to analysis, the average annual growth of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan after the pandemic has exceeded 20 percent. From January to November of this year, 6 million 134 thousand foreign citizens have visited the country. It is estimated that this figure will reach 7 million by the end of the year. Comparing the current numbers with the results from the first 11 months of 2022, it can be observed that the number of tourists arriving from certain countries has increased several fold this year.

When analyzed by country, this year, compared to the first 11 months of 2022, our country was visited by 676 thousand tourists from Russia (1.3 times more), 99 thousand from Turkey (1.4 times more), 41 thousand from India (2.9 times more), 39 thousand from China (8.5 times more), 35 thousand from South Korea (1.9 times more), 28 thousand from Germany (1.7 times more), 25 thousand from Italy (2.9 times more), 22 thousand from the USA (1.8 times more), and 18 thousand from France (1.7 times more).

One of the important factors in tourism is accommodation. Tourists pay attention to even the smallest details when using hotel services.

To date, 183 new hotels (with 11,342 beds) and 207 hostels (with 7,237 beds) have been newly opened in the regions. The total number of accommodation facilities has reached 5,365, with the number of beds in them reaching 142,038. In residential areas, 333 family guesthouses (with 3,092 beds) have been established, bringing their total number to 3,305 (with 29,300 beds). As a result of setting up 810 new tourist organizations and travel agencies serving tourists, their number has increased to 2,649 [16].

The «Tabarruk ziyorat» (Sacred Pilgrimage) platform has been launched in 7 languages spoken by member states of the Organization of Turkic States, and in its initial stage, 100 pilgrimage sites in the country were included on the platform.

Today, there are more than 8,000 cultural heritage sites and 122 museums in our country.

In the future, it is planned to create a comprehensive database on the history, monuments, and attractions of 31 districts and 143 tourist mahallas, to develop tourist packages based on this information in 12 languages, and to train employees of tourism and service facilities.

The average expenditure of one tourist during their stay in the country is 326 dollars. In 2021, this figure was 224 dollars.

Moreover, when this indicator is analyzed by country of origin, a tourist from the Far East and European countries spends \$1,066 (compared to \$709 in 2021), while those from CIS countries spend \$743 (compared to \$635 in 2021). Visitors from neighboring countries spend between \$154 and \$257. It should also be noted that tourism services worth 2 billion dollars were provided in the first 11 months of this year. In 2024, measures will be taken to increase tourism exports to 2.5 billion US dollars. Efforts will be made to increase the number of foreign tourists to 10 million [17].

In conclusion, it can be said that tourism is a comprehensive sector with both economic and socio-cultural significance, ranking third in the world in terms of profitability. Another important aspect is that it allows for the creation of many jobs with minimal costs. Due to Uzbekistan's high tourism potential, this sector is developing steadily. Uzbekistan has been included in the list of the world's best tourist destinations. Tashkent, as the capital and one of the

ancient cities of Uzbekistan, primarily receives a large number of foreign and domestic tourists from countries around the world and within the republic.

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